

IR, PMR and TG Studies on Substituted 1,3,5-Triphenylformazans Complexes with Bivalent Cobalt, Nickel, Copper and Zinc

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Manuscript received 8 June 1992, accepted 17 September 1992

1,3,5-Triphenylformazan complexes with bivalent Co, Ni, Cu and Zn have been prepared. Both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes were isolated. The pmr spectra show the displacement of one proton from the carboxylic group of substituted phenyl ring and the second proton from the imino group to form 1 : 1 complex. For 1 : 2 (M : L) complex the number of aromatic protons (C-H) is increased to double that for (1 : 1) plus two. The structure of the solid complexes was also elucidated using ir spectroscopy. The presence of water and ethanol molecules and their situation within the formed complexes have been established by TG.

Triphenylformazans are used as chromophoric indicators for metal ions¹. Yurchenko *et al.*² studied the uv spectra of some substituted formazans and their nickel complexes in different solvents. Ir studies of some formazan derivatives led to the conclusion that the heterocyclic system has an asymmetric distribution of electron density³. Mester *et al.*⁴ studied the pmr spectra of several sugar and non-sugar formazans. Badawy *et al.*⁵ studied the solid complexes of two derivatives of 1,5-diaryl-3-acetylformazan with lanthanide metal ions. Some derivatives of 3-cyanofomazans have been prepared and their metal complexes investigated⁶.

The present investigation deals with the preparation and investigation of the molecular structure of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with 1-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-3-aryl-5-phenylformazans, where aryl = Ph (1a), *p*-Cl-Ph (1b), *p*-CH₃-Ph (1c), *p*-NO₂-Ph (1d) and *p*-OMe-Ph (1e).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the formazans are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE
TRIPHENYLFORMAZANS (a-e)

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	N
(a) C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	180-81 ^a	69.20 (69.76)	4.50 4.68	16.40 16.27
(b) C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ^b	205-07	63.10 (63.41)	3.76 3.96	15.10 14.80
(c) C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	178	70.30 (70.39)	5.70 5.03	15.22 15.64
(d) C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄	212	61.43 (61.70)	3.50 3.86	17.40 17.99
(e) C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	163	67.60 (67.38)	4.70 4.81	15.05 14.97

^aLit.¹¹ 181-82°. ^bFound : Cl, 9.70 ; calcd. 9.38%.

Ir spectra : A group of broad ir bands at 2 500-3 000 cm⁻¹ of compounds 1a-e may be assigned to the NH⁺ group, which may be originated through the formation of zwitterion through the transfer of a proton from the carboxylic group to one of the nitrogen atoms in the formazan chain.

The presence of medium bands at 3 300 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) (carboxylic OH) indicates that the COOH group exists in the acid form and ionised form. This is confirmed by investigating the C=O band which is observed at its characteristic position. The band at 1 670 cm⁻¹ with two weak shoulders at higher and lower wavenumbers at 1 680-1 650 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the isomerisation of the carboxylic group, thus confirming the aforementioned equilibrium. The other bands are observed at 3 050-3 070 (NH) and 1 450-1 440 cm⁻¹ (N=N).

The band observed at 3 090-3 050 cm⁻¹ (NH) in the free ligand, disappears on complexation indicating the participation of NH group in chelation. This is confirmed by disappearance of the δ_{NH} band (1 600 cm⁻¹) of the ligand in the spectra of the complexes. The bands assigned to NH⁺ are not observed as a result of chelation. Also, the band due to carboxylic group accompanied by the formation of the zwitterion is not observed indicating the participation of the *ortho*-carboxylic group in the complex formation. The existence of very weak bands at about 3 500 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the presence of ethyl alcohol molecule. The N=N band is shifted to lower wavenumber from 1 400-1 450 cm⁻¹ in case of free ligand to 1 350-1 400 cm⁻¹ indicating its contribution in chelation with the central metal ion.

For the 1 : 2 complexes, the NH bands observed as a weak band in position slightly shifted from their expected values. This may be taken as evidence for the existence of NH group in the complex molecules. However, no bands due to solvent or

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF 1a-e AND THEIR COMPLEXES

1a	1b	1c	1d	1e	Assignment
(A) Free ligands					
3 400	3 400	3 400	3 300	3 300	νNH
3 050	3 050	3 050	3 050	3 050	νNH
3 000-2 500	3 000-2 800	3 000-2 800	3 000-2 800	3 000-2 800	νNH
1 670	1 670	1 670	1 670	1 670	νC=O
1 600	1 600	1 600	1 600	1 600	δNH
1 450	1 450	1 450	1 450	1 450	ν _{as} (N=N)
—	740	—	—	—	νC-C1
—	—	—	—	1 030	νC-OCH ₃
—	—	—	1 320	—	νC-NO ₂
—	—	2 980-2 860	—	—	νC-CH ₃
(B) 1 : 1 (M : L) Cu complexes					
3 540	3 450	3 450	3 450	3 550	νOH(C ₂ H ₅ OH)
1 590	1 590	1 690	1 600	1 590	δOH(C ₂ H ₅ OH)
1 380	1 350	1 400	1 350	1 400	ν _{as} (N=N)
830	830	820	810	820	γOH
(C) 1 : 2 (M : L) Cu complexes					
3 050	3 050	3 050	3 050	3 050	νNH
1 850	1 600	1 600	1 580	1 580	δNH
1 400	1 440	1 450	1 440	1 410	ν _{as} (N=N)
Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Assignment	
(A) 1 : 1 (M : L)					
3 525	3 525	3 525	3 525	νOH(C ₂ H ₅ OH)	
1 590	1 580	1 580	1 580	δOH(C ₂ H ₅ OH)	
1 440	1 440	1 440	1 440	ν _{as} (N=H)	
830	830	830	830	γOH	
(B) 1 : 2 (M : L)					
3 050	3 050	3 050	3 050	νNH	
1 600	1 605	1 600	1 600	δNH	
1 430	1 430	1 430	1 430	ν _{as} (N=N)	

water molecules were observed. For the 1 : 2 complex the ν_{OH} bands were not observed indicating that COOH group is involved in complexation. The bands of N=N group are shifted to lower wavenumber values. Table 2 lists important ir bands of formazan derivatives (1a-e) and their copper complexes and that of 1d-complexes with Co, Ni and Zn ions.

Thermogravimetric analysis: This method of analysis opens up new possibilities for the investigation of metal complexes⁷. The weight-loss from ambient temperature upto 500° was scanned with a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹. The initial weight-loss occurring at 30-140° is interpreted as the loss of moisture and hygroscopic water during the drying of the complexes. The TG curves show decomposition of the organic part of the chelates within the temperature range 200-310°. At the final stage (380-450°), the metal oxide residue was formed due to the stoichiometric CuO. For the 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-(1b-e) complexes, the first decomposition state indicating a loss percent of 4.00, 8.50, 11.50 and 8.00 at 30-140°, is mainly attributed to the loss of 1, 2, 3 and 2 molecules of water of hydration for 1b, 1c, 1d and 1e respectively. In the second decomposition state (200-310°), a loss of 11.0, 11.0, 9.0 and 10.0% is mainly attributed to the loss of one coordinated ethanol molecule. In all the complexes under investigation at temperature range (380-450°) CuO is formed as the final product.

The results of the mass obtained by TG are in good agreement with the values calculated using the results of microchemical analysis for these complexes and with those obtained by determination⁸ of the metal ion content after decomposition of the chelates.

Pmr spectra: Pmr spectra of all ligands (Table 3) exhibit a multiplet signal at δ 6.8-8.8 which is attributed to the aromatic protons (C-H) and the -NH proton. Formazans 1b, 1d and 1e show singlet at δ 15.3, 10.9 and 10.2 respectively. These signals may be assigned to the ionisable proton of COOH, since they disappear after deuteration. The deuteration of 1b, 1d and 1e leads to some variation of multiplet signals which can be taken as a criterion for the partial ionisation nature of the NH group.

In the pmr spectra of Ni-1d (1 : 1) and Zn-1d (1 : 1), the singlet band at δ 10.9 disappeared and the multiplet is shifted to higher field. This is an indication that the two protons of COOH and NH groups are involved in chelation. The alcohol molecules involved in chelation show a sharp band at δ 3.4 due to 5H of aliphatic protons of ethyl alcohol involved in chelation (Table 3) to satisfy the coordination centers of the respective metal ions. Based on the above finding, one can conclude that the reaction of 1,3,5-triphenylformazan with Ni^{II} or

TABLE 3—PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME FORMAZANS AND THEIR Ni AND Zn COMPLEXES

Compd.	δ
1b	7.1–8.2 (14H, m, aromatic C–H and NH) 15.3 (1H, s, carboxylic OH)
1d	6.8–8.1 (14H, m, aromatic C–H and NH) 10.9 (1H, s, carboxylic OH)
1e	6.8–8 (14H, m, aromatic C–H and NH) 10.2 (1H, s, carboxylic OH)
Zn-1d (1 : 1)	2.4 (3H, s, (OCH ₃) protons) 6.8–8.4 (13H, m, aromatic C–H) 3.4 (5H, alcoholic C–H)
Zn-1d (1 : 2)	2.6 (4H, CH ₃ of solvent+alc.OH)
Ni-1d (1 : 1)	6.7–8.4 (28H, m, aromatic C–H and NH) 3.4 (5H, alcoholic C–H)
Ni-1d (1 : 2)	2.6 (4H, CH ₃ of solvent+alc.OH) 3.4 (5H, alcoholic C–H)
Ni-1d (1 : 2)	6.7–8.4 (28H, m, aromatic C–H and NH)

Zn^{II} to form 1 : 1 (M : L) complex is accompanied by the displacement of one proton from the carboxylic group of *ortho*-substituted phenyl ring and the second proton from the imino group in addition to the coordination bond with N⁵ of the formazan chain and one bond with H₂O or C₂H₅OH molecule to form 1 : 1 complex.

For the 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes (e.g. Zn-1d and Ni-1d complexes) the group of signals at δ 6.7–8.4 is increased in comparison with those of the free ligands and 1 : 1 complex. From the integration values, it is clear that the number of aromatic C–H proton is increased to double that for (1 : 1) plus two (13×2+2) as shown in Table 3. They are attributed to the aromatic C–H and N–H protons, which confirms the formation of 1 : 2 (M : L) complex. The existence of two extraprotons is in accordance with the assumption that the NH proton is not participating in chelation.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of the highest purity available. The 1,3,5-triphenylformazan and its derivatives (1a–e) were obtained by coupling the diazotised anthranilic acid (0.01 mol) prepared in the usual manner with substituted benzaldehyde phenylhydrazone (0.01 mol) dissolved in sodium hydroxide. The resulting formazan solutions were acidified with dilute (1 : 1) HCl. The product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to constant

melting point⁹. The purity of the resulting formazans was confirmed by elemental analysis (Table 1). The ligands are considered as newly prepared derivatives, not cited in the literature.

A stock solution (10⁻³ M) of each formazan was prepared in ethanol. Stock solutions (~10⁻² M) of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared and standardised using EDTA¹⁰.

The complexes were prepared by mixing hot saturated alcoholic solutions of 0.005 mole cobalt, nickel, copper or zinc sulphate (0.005 mol) with the requisited amount of the ligands (1a–e) sufficient to form 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 complex. The solid complexes separated on standing were washed with water and alcohol.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 1100 and Beckman infrared spectrophotometers and pmr spectra (DMSO) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

Thermogravimetric analysis was performed on a Du-Pont 1090 thermal analyser. The weight-loss was measured from ambient temperature up to 900° in a heating rate of 10° per min.

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